

IMPROVEMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL SERVICES IN PHARMACIES

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Relevance: Pharmaceutical services in pharmacies represent a crucial component of the healthcare system, ensuring the rational use of medicines, optimizing pharmacotherapy, and improving the overall quality of patient care.

Purpose. To identify and substantiate modern approaches aimed at improving the quality, accessibility, and effectiveness of pharmaceutical services in community and hospital pharmacies.

Materials and Methods. The study is based on a comprehensive analysis of scientific publications, regulatory frameworks, and international guidelines, as well as surveys conducted among practicing pharmacists and pharmacy visitors.

Results. The findings indicate that the integration of clinical pharmacy principles, the expansion of pharmaceutical counseling practices, the implementation of digital health technologies (such as e-prescriptions and electronic drug databases), and continuous professional development of pharmacists significantly contribute to the enhancement of service quality. Moreover, these measures strengthen the role of pharmacists in rational pharmacotherapy and patient-centered care.

Conclusions. The improvement of pharmaceutical services in pharmacies is a strategic priority for modern healthcare systems. It ensures the effective use of medicines, fosters public trust in pharmacy professionals, and supports the sustainable development of national healthcare.